

PRINCIPLES OF INTERNATIONAL ACCOUNTING

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Annotation: This article discusses the need for a transition to International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) in Uzbekistan and the challenges of accounting in the transition to IFRSs.

Keywords: IFRS, investment, accounting, tax authorities, qualified personnel, stock exchanges, international organization, transformation.

INTRODUCTION

Just as English is a universal language, International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) are a universal business language. These standards define how companies prepare their financial statements. Reporting based on these standards is understood around the world.

By accelerating the transition to international financial reporting standards, it is possible to provide foreign investors with the necessary information environment and expand access to international financial markets, as well as to improve the system of training specialists in accounting and auditing in accordance with international standards. [1]

REFERENCES

In accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 24, 2020 No PP-4611 "On additional measures for the transition to International Financial Reporting Standards" Joint-stock companies, commercial banks, insurance organizations and legal entities included in the category of large taxpayers from January 1, 2021 organized accounting on the basis of IFRS, and from the end of 2021 began to prepare financial statements on the basis of IFRS.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

The transition to the IFRS will benefit the economy, on the one hand, by expanding relations with international financial institutions such as the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, the World Bank, the Asian Development Bank, the International Monetary Fund and others, and attracting foreign investment. improves the country's investment climate. At the same time, IFRS plays an important role in raising accounting to the international level. On the other hand, it will increase the workload and expenditures of joint-stock companies, commercial banks, insurance companies and legal entities included in the category of large taxpayers.

The state is interested in accounting in accordance with IFRSs in terms of attracting investment; Investors and founders are interested in having control over the use of their funds, access to accurate and objective, transparent information at no additional cost, otherwise they will have to pay more. will have to spend money to transform the reports. Finally, the use of reporting data based on IFRSs is an important factor in the adoption of objective management decisions, strategic plans in the management of the enterprise.

The following definitions of international financial reporting standards are provided by economists:

“International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) are a system of generally accepted requirements, principles, rules and procedures that define a common approach to the preparation of financial statements that is useful to a wide range of interested users.” [2]

"International Financial Reporting Standards is a separate branch of the discipline of financial accounting and reporting, which is part of the study of the conceptual framework of financial reporting, the need for international financial reporting standards, their development, content, interpretation and application of methodological issues." . [3]

The prospective foreign investor does not understand the reports prepared by Uzbek organizations and therefore does not believe that the figures are accurate. Converting and auditing reports to IFRS can be labor-intensive, time-consuming and costly. For example, Rothschild & So Investment Bank (financial adviser), Dentons law firm (legal adviser), as well as KPMG (preparation of financial and tax reports, as well as the state in the charter capital of the company) were selected to sell the state share in the Sosa-Sola plant in Uzbekistan. leading international consultants were involved. [4]

Uzbekistan has tried to switch to IFRS before. Joint-stock companies and banks were required to submit IFRS-based financial statements in practice. Unfortunately, these reports are often prepared with the help of international audit organizations, and the quality of the reports prepared by the organizations themselves is unsatisfactory.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The following problems arise when switching to IFRS:

- Changes in existing accounting regulations;
- Lack of highly qualified personnel in the transition to IFRS;
- Lack of quality textbooks for studying IFRS in Uzbek;
- Lack of knowledge of foreign languages (English, Russian);

- High costs of both parallel accounting on the basis of IFRSs and IFRSs and transformation of reports on the basis of IFRS;
- Management's opposition to full and transparent disclosure;
- Lack of a clear form of reporting forms for industries and sectors based on IFRSs.

In solving the problems that arise during the transition to IFRS, the following should be taken into account:

- Introduction of a national certification system to address staff shortages in the transition to IFRS;
- Reporting to IFRS managers on the basis of IFRS is important not only for investors and external users, but also for making the right decisions in the management of the enterprise;

Increasing the interest of business leaders in the presentation of factual and real information in financial statements.

Literature :

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